

THYROID DISORDERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO HYPOTHYROIDISM: A REVIEW

***Kanishkar P. R., Sabapathi P.**

Department of Pharmacology, JKK Munirajah Institute of Health Sciences College of
Pharmacy, T.N Palayam, Erode (DT), Tamilnadu.

Article Received on 28 April 2026,
Article Revised on 18 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20443549>

*Corresponding Author

Kanishkar

Department of Pharmacology, JKK
Munirajah Institute of Health Sciences
College of Pharmacy, T.N Palayam,
Erode (DT), Tamilnadu.

How To Cite This Article: *Kanishkar P. R.,
Sabapathi P. (2026). Thyroid Disorders with
Special Reference to Hypothyroidism: A
Review. World Journal of Pharmacy and
Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 247–257.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

One clinical condition that primary care doctors frequently see is hypothyroidism. Infertility, dyslipidaemia, hypertension, cognitive decline, and neuromuscular dysfunction can all be consequences of untreated hypothyroidism. One in 300 Americans may have hypothyroidism, according to data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. Levothyroxine, a synthetic version of tetraiodothyronine, replaced thyroid extract therapy in the 1970s. There hasn't been any significant advancement in hypothyroidism therapy since then. There is disagreement about the biological definition of subclinical hypothyroidism. Thyroid gland autoimmune damage, prior thyroid surgery, and radioiodine treatment are major causes of hypothyroidism. Several drugs, such as lithium, amiodarone, and cytokines, frequently cause hypothyroidism. Congenital hypothyroidism that goes away on

its own within the first few months or years of life is known as transient congenital hypothyroidism (TCH). There are currently few accurate indicators that indicate TCH at diagnosis, and the diagnosis is made when levothyroxine medication is stopped at the age of three. To examine hypothyroidism, a prevalent ailment in primary care, including its causes, consequences, diagnosis, and available treatments, such as levothyroxine, while emphasizing areas that require further development.

KEYWORDS: Hypothyroidism, Thyroid Disorders, TSH (Thyroid Stimulating Hormone), T3 and T4 hormones.

INTRODUCTION

The inability of the thyroid gland to generate enough thyroid hormone to satisfy the body's metabolic needs is known as hypothyroidism. Infertility, dyslipidaemia, hypertension, cognitive decline, and neuromuscular dysfunction can all be consequences of untreated hypothyroidism. According to data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III), hypothyroidism affects almost 1 in 300 Americans.¹ The frequency is higher in women than in men and rises with age.² Approximately 13 million Americans are thought to suffer undiagnosed hypothyroidism.^[5] Clinical conditions resulting from TH deficiency will vary depending on the severity and duration of the deficiency, affecting almost all tissues to varying degrees. However, because these hormones play a fundamental role in normal fetal brain development, the lack of adequate TH production determines more detrimental consequences during intrauterine life.² The advent of molecular biology brought significant advances regarding information regarding the disease, including elucidations regarding its ethology, which may have originated during intrauterine life.^[8] deficiency. Goitre is typically endemic in regions where daily iodine intake is 50 mg, and congenital hypothyroidism is observed when daily consumption is 25 mg. In regions with severe iodine shortage, goitre prevalence can reach 80%. In South-East Asia, Latin America, and Central Africa, populations that are most vulnerable are typically isolated and reside in hilly regions. Iodization programs have been shown to be beneficial in lowering the size of goitres and preventing the development of goitres and cretinism in youngsters. Iodization programs can also cause thyrotoxicosis, particularly in older people, and autonomy can develop in nodular goitres, which can occasionally result in thyrotoxicosis. Nodular goitres for forty years.^[1]

Thyroid hormone's effects on the heart and circulatory system are known to cause some of the most distinctive and prevalent signs and symptoms of thyroid disease.^[2] Primary gland failure or inadequate pituitary or hypothalamic activation of the thyroid gland can result in hypothyroidism. Congenital defects, autoimmune destruction (Hashimoto disease), iodine shortage, and infiltrative illnesses can all lead to primary gland failure. The most frequent cause of hypothyroidism in the US is autoimmune thyroid disease.^[5]

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

All the T₄ and about 20% of the T₃ in the blood are generated by the thyroid gland; the remaining T₃ is created peripherally by T₄ deiodination. There is significant physiological

regulation that is tissue-specific, even though circulating T3 levels are essential for systemic thyroid hormone action [16, 31]. Furthermore, the majority of research concentrates on T3 as the primary mediator of thyroid hormone signalling; however, a 2021 study suggests that T4 may be able to cause biological effects that differ from those caused by T3.^[7] The manufacture of TH, the only compounds in our bodies that contain iodine in their configuration, need iodine. Iodized salt and bread are dietary sources of iodine. and dairy goods. The World Health Organization recommends a daily consumption of iodine of at least 75 µg, or 10 g of iodized salt (one part sodium iodide in 100,000 parts NaCl).^[8] The lack of large cohort studies examining the pathophysiology of TCH is regrettable; one of the primary obstacles to prospective research is the requirement for CH patients. should be reevaluated at age three to determine if thyroid impairment is transient. As a result, anecdotal reports of well-characterized instances or small case series provide most of the data supporting the determinants of TCH. The pathophysiology of TCH has been linked to both hereditary and environmental factors, the majority of which have an impact on the thyroid hormone biosynthetic pathway.^[11] The thyroid gland produces and secretes the thyroid hormones T4 (the prohormone) and T3 (the active hormone) at a molar ratio of around 11 to 1 (20). Only a little portion of T4 and T3 circulate as unbound free T4 and T3 (FT4 and FT3, respectively) in serum; the majority of T4 and T3 are bound to transportation proteins TBG, albumin, and transthyretin.^[14] Iodothyronine deiodinase type 1 (DIO1) and type 2 (DIO2) are expressed in several tissues, enabling the tissues to convert T4 to T3 and put T3 back into the bloodstream. T3 generated in the brain, pituitary, and brown adipose tissue by DIO2 stays in the tissue much longer and can start thyroid hormone signalling locally, while T3 produced in the liver via DIO1 returns quickly to the circulation, according to studies employing rat models [33, 34]. This is due to the fact that DIO2 is found in the endoplasmic reticulum, which is intimately connected to the nucleus, while DIO1 is found in the cellular plasma membrane³⁵. Thus, the total amount of incoming T3 from the blood (which typically makes up about 50% of the thyroid hormone) defines thyroid hormone signalling in tissues that express DIO2.^[7]

HYPOTHYROIDISM

Spontaneous hypothyroidism is more prevalent in elderly women and is ten times more common in women than in males in iodine-replete cultures, where its incidence ranges from 1 to 2%. According to two studies conducted in Northern Europe, Japan, and the USA, the frequency ranges from 0.6 to 12 per 1000 women and from 1.3 to 4.0 per 1000 males (Table 1). Surveys of senior citizens in the community show a higher occurrence. In Leiden, the

Netherlands, 7% of 558 people between the ages of 85 and 89 had overt hypothyroidism.¹⁵ In regions with iodine deficiency, the prevalence is lower.^[1] Numerous case studies have shown that hypothyroidism may result in a lengthening of the QT interval that predisposes the patient to ventricular excitability, in contrast to hyperthyroidism, which can induce atrial arrhythmias. *Torsade de pointes* is a rare side effect that can be treated. Changes in cardiac gene expression, particularly decreased expression of the sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase and increased expression of its inhibitor, phospholamban, contribute to the decreased ventricular contractility linked to hypothyroidism.^[2] The major causes of hypothyroidism are listed in Box. Autoimmune thyroiditis is the most prevalent cause of hypothyroidism in industrialized nations, and it may involve connected to either thyroid atrophy or a goitre (Hashimoto's thyroiditis) equally often. Many people with hypothyroidism are additionally treated with radioiodine ablation or surgical thyroidectomy for hyperthyroidism or thyroid malignancy. Less frequently, hypothyroidism can be brought on by drugs (which may be reversible) or develop because of pituitary or hypothalamic abnormalities (central or secondary hypothyroidism). Congenital hypothyroidism affects one out of every 4000 live births and is caused by either thyroid aplasia or hypoplasia or abnormal thyroid hormone production.⁶ Iodine deficiency is still quite common in various regions of the world, which causes hypothyroidism and developmental abnormalities in newborns and children.^[6]

Table I: Common symptoms of hypothyroidism.

1. Arthralgias
2. Cold intolerance*
3. Constipation
4. Depression
5. Difficulty concentrating
6. Menorrhagia
7. Myalgias
8. Weight gain
9. Dry skin
10. Fatigue*

SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDIS

Hypothyroidism The observation of elevated serum thyrotropin (TSH) but normal free thyroxine (T₄) is referred to as subclinical hypothyroidism. Within Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis is the most prevalent cause in the population. Subclinical hypothyroidism affected 8% of women (10% of women over 55) and 3% of males in the original Whickham study conducted in Northeast England.⁷ 9.4% of the participants in the Colorado research had

elevated blood TSH levels, and 9.0% of them had subclinical hypothyroidism.^[1] This classification is used for asymptomatic patients with slightly elevated TSH levels and normal T3 and T4 levels. This kind of hypothyroidism is regarded as mild and to serve as a risk factor for the development of overt hypothyroidism and other dysfunctions. The definition of normal TH levels—more especially, TSH levels—is where diagnostic implications begin. Traditionally, high concentrations of TSH have been diagnosed using the established cut-off point for normal TSH levels, which is 4 to 5 mU/L. It has been suggested that normal TSH levels be maintained at 0.4–4 mU/L since some studies have investigated lower cutoff points, of 2 to 2.5 mU/L, but the arguments for adopting such values were deemed insufficient. There would probably be more drawbacks than benefits to classifying findings between 2 and 4 mU/L as abnormal and then introducing treatment in these situations.^[8] With normal thyroid hormone levels and slightly raised blood TSH concentrations, SHYPO is a state of mild to severe thyroid insufficiency. Recently, a panel of specialists separated patients with Hypo into two groups: those with mildly elevated serum TSH levels (4.5–10 mIU/liter) and those with more significantly elevated levels (10 mIU/liter) (6). Using these criteria of thyroid hormone shortage, we will look at the course of the illness, its side effects, and its therapy.^[3]

A biochemical diagnosis of subclinical hypothyroidism is characterized by a normal-range free T4 level and an increased TSH. level. Patients may or may not have hypothyroidism-related symptoms. Many patients' TSH levels may spontaneously return to normal upon retesting. However, the factor most significantly linked to the development of overt hypothyroidism in a prospective analysis of 107 individuals over 55 was an initial TSH level more than 10 to 15 mIU/L.^[5]

CLINICAL SIGNS OF HYPOTHYROIDISM

Bradycardia
Coarse facies
Cognitive impairment
Diastolic hypertension
Oedema
Goitre
Hypothermia
Laboratory results

- Elevated C-reactive protein
- Hyperprolactinaemia
- Hyponatraemia
- Increased creatine kinase
- Increased low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
- Increased triglycerides
- Normocytic anaemia
- Proteinuria

DIAGNOSIS

Every patient exhibiting signs of hypothyroidism should have thyroid dysfunction evaluated by family doctors. The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force concluded that there is not enough data to support regular screening for hypothyroidism in asymptomatic people, and the American Academy of Family Physicians does not advise doing so.³ Patients with risk factors for hypothyroidism, such as a history of autoimmune disease, head or neck radiation, prior radioactive iodine therapy, the presence of a goitre, a family history of thyroid disease, or treatment with medications known to affect thyroid function, may be screened even if they are asymptomatic.^[5] A rise in the blood thyroid stimulating hormone concentration over the upper limit of the test confirms the diagnosis of primary hypothyroidism. range of reference. Thyroid stimulating hormone levels over 10 mU/l and a decrease in serum free or total thyroxine concentrations below the standard range are common in adults with symptomatic hypothyroidism. Some persons may not have severe hypothyroidism; their serum thyroxine concentration is within the reference range, but their serum thyroid stimulating hormone is elevated (usually between 5 and 10 mU/l). This condition, known as subclinical hypothyroidism (also known as mild hypothyroidism), is indicative of compensated or mild thyroid failure in many people. Roughly thirty percent Thyroid stimulating hormone levels fluctuate throughout the day, peaking at night and falling around 2:00 pm. This fluctuation is preserved in moderate hypothyroidism, occasionally creating the appearance of an illness that fluctuates.^[6] Down syndrome, Beckwith syndrome, mucopolysaccharidoses, chondrodysplasia, hypopituitarism, and obesity should all be included in the differential diagnosis. It is always crucial. should keep in mind that obesity is seldom linked to hypothyroidism.^[8] Therefore, when older individuals exhibit one or more symptoms or indications, thyroid function problems should be checked for. via hypothyroidism. Practically speaking, first-line biochemical screening for older individuals with vague clinical symptoms should include thyroid function assays.^[9]

TREATMENT

Treating hypothyroidism in older patients is a common duty that should be carried out in institutions as well as in general and special practice. Treatment for hypothyroidism in older patients is frequently effective, straightforward, and affordable with a little care. However, certain patients can have issues, and the best method of replacement is now being debated.^[9] Most of hypothyroid individuals will need thyroid hormone therapy for the rest of their lives (Figure 213,19–24). Two thyroid hormones are produced by a healthy thyroid gland: T4 as

well as triiodothyronine (T3). T3 is the physiologically active version, even though T4 is generated in larger quantities. Deiodinase enzymes convert T4 peripherally to produce around 80% of T3. However, once-daily synthetic thyroxine preparations are used almost exclusively to treat hypothyroidism due to the short biologic half-lives of T3 preparations.^[5] In patients receiving L-T4 treatment, total T4 and FT4 levels were often elevated at that time. The first investigations demonstrated the detrimental effects of TSH suppression on the heart, liver, and bone by the early 1990s after the more sensitive TSH test became accessible in 1980. The first double-blind controlled trials assessed the effects of L-T4 in individuals with Hypo between 1990 and 2000. The first double-blind crossover trial to evaluate the effects of combined treatment with T3 and T4 in hypothyroid patients was published in 1970 by Smith *et al.*^[12] Biological and synthetic thyroid hormone treatments including T4 and T3 were not recommended in the 1995 American Thyroid Association (ATA) recommendations, repaired due to varying and often elevated blood T3 levels (71). The American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists (ATA) stated in 2012 that "desiccated thyroid hormone should not be used for the treatment of hypothyroidism" and that evidence does not support the use of synthetic combination therapies. The ATA also continued to recommend L-thyroxine monotherapy.^[13] Due to the possibility of bradycardia in individuals with long-term hypothyroidism, which might conceal significant but asymptomatic damage, levothyrox. Patients who are older than 60 or who have a history of ischemic heart disease should replace their ine with caution. Those with severe and chronic hypothyroidism (thyroid stimulating hormone level >50 mU/l) require extra care. The first dose of levothyroxine should be 12.5 or 25 µg per day in these cases, or in a person with active angina pectoris or recent acute coronary syndrome. This dose should then be raised every three to six weeks until euthyroid is attained.^[6]

Figure 1: Proportion of dissatisfaction expressed by patients with self-reported hypothyroidism by type of treatment for hypothyroidism.

a | The percentage of respondents who were unhappy in each of the four categories—weight, exhaustion, mood, and memory. Levothyroxine (n = 6,949), levothyroxine and liothyronine combination therapy (n = 978), or desiccated thyroid extract (DTE) (n = 3,239) were the three therapies given to respondents. An asterisk denotes that the values for DTE were statistically significantly different ($P < 0.05$) to other treatments.

b | The percentage of unhappy respondents (left) who received DTE (n = 123), levothyroxine (n = 677), levothyroxine and liothyronine combo treatment (n = 124), or liothyronine (n = 45). The identical patient groups' quality of life (QOL) scores are shown on the right. The highest QOL is represented by a score of 100, while the lowest is represented by a score of 0. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between levothyroxine and DTE (* $P = 0.010$) and levothyroxine and the combination of levothyroxine and liothyronine (** $P = 0.001$).^[7]

Treatment of primary hypothyroidism

Figure 2: Algorithm for the treatment of primary hypothyroidism.

CAUSES OF HYPOTHYROIDISM

The major causes of hypothyroidism are listed in Box. Autoimmune thyroiditis, which can be linked to a goitre (Hashimoto's thyroiditis) or, as frequently, thyroid atrophy, is the most prevalent cause of hypothyroidism in industrialized nations. Many people with hypothyroidism are additionally treated with radioiodine ablation or surgical thyroidectomy for hyperthyroidism or thyroid malignancy. Less frequently, hypothyroidism can be brought on by drugs (which may be reversible) or develop because of pituitary or hypothalamic abnormalities (central or secondary hypothyroidism). Congenital hypothyroidism affects one out of every 4000 live births and is caused by either thyroid aplasia or hypoplasia or abnormal thyroid hormone production.^[6] Iodine deficiency is still quite common in various regions of the world, which causes hypothyroidism and developmental abnormalities in newborns and children.^[6]

These can be atrogenic conditions, such as those brought on by radioactive iodine, antithyroid medication treatment, or surgical procedures. Although it is uncommon, hypothyroidism brought on by excessive iodine-containing medication use should be considered.^[8]

CAUSES OF HYPERTHYROIDISM

Figure 3: Causes of hyperthyroidism.

CONCLUSION

Low thyroid hormone production is the cause of hypothyroidism, a common thyroid condition. It can affect many body functions and may lead to problems such as tiredness,

weight gain, depression, and heart-related complications if not treated properly. Early diagnosis using TSH, T3, and T4 tests helps in effective management of the disease. The primary medication used to manage hypothyroidism and enhance the patient's quality of life is levothyroxine. To avoid problems, proper care, frequent monitoring, and patient awareness are crucial. To enhance diagnostic and treatment techniques for improved patient care, more research is required.

REFERENCE

1. Vanderpump MP. The epidemiology of thyroid disease. *British medical bulletin*, 2011 Sep 1; 99(1).
2. Klein I, Danzi S. Thyroid disease and the heart. *Circulation*. 2007 Oct 9; 116(15): 1725-35.
3. Biondi B, Cooper DS. The clinical significance of subclinical thyroid dysfunction. *Endocrine reviews*. 2008 Feb 1; 29(1): 76-131.
4. Biondi B. Mechanisms in endocrinology: heart failure and thyroid dysfunction. *European journal of endocrinology*. 2012 Nov; 167(5): 609-18.
5. Gaitonde DY, Rowley KD, Sweeney LB. Hypothyroidism: an update. *South African Family Practice*. 2012 Sep 1; 54(5): 384-90.
6. Vaidya B, Pearce SH. Management of hypothyroidism in adults. *Bmj*. 2008 Jul 28; 337.
7. Hegedüs L, Bianco AC, Jonklaas J, Pearce SH, Weetman AP, Perros P. Primary hypothyroidism and quality of life. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*. 2022 Apr; 18(4): 230-42.
8. Setian N. Hypothyroidism in children: diagnosis and treatment. *Jornal de pediatria*. 2007; 83: S209-16.
9. Laurberg P, Andersen S, Pedersen IB, Carlé A. Hypothyroidism in the elderly: pathophysiology, diagnosis and treatment. *Drugs & aging*. 2005 Jan; 22(1): 23-38.
10. Yamada M, Mori M. Mechanisms related to the pathophysiology and management of central hypothyroidism. *Nature clinical practice Endocrinology & metabolism*. 2008 Dec; 4(12): 683-94.
11. Peters C, Schoenmakers N. Mechanisms in endocrinology: the pathophysiology of transient congenital hypothyroidism. *European journal of endocrinology*. 2022 Aug; 187(2): R1-6.
12. Biondi B, Wartofsky L. Treatment With Thyroid Hormone. *Endocrine Reviews*. 2014; 35(3): 433–512.

13. McAninch EA, Bianco AC. The History and Future of Treatment of Hypothyroidism. *Annals of Internal Medicine*. 2016; 164(1): 50–56.
14. Lauffer P, Zwaveling-Soonawala N, Naafs JC, Boelen A, Van Trotsenburg AP. Diagnosis and management of central congenital hypothyroidism. *Frontiers in endocrinology*. 2021 Sep 9; 12: 686317.
15. Chakera AJ, Pearce SH, Vaidya B. Treatment for primary hypothyroidism: current approaches and future possibilities. *Drug design, development and therapy*. 2011 Dec 22: 1-1.
16. Chu JW, Crapo LM. The treatment of subclinical hypothyroidism is seldom necessary. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2001 Oct 1; 86(10): 4591-9.
17. Calsolaro V, Niccolai F, Pasqualetti G, Tognini S, Magno S, Riccioni T, Bottari M, Caraccio N, Monzani F. Hypothyroidism in the elderly: who should be treated and how?. *Journal of the Endocrine Society*. 2019 Jan; 3(1): 146-58.
18. Bianco AC. Emerging therapies in hypothyroidism. *Annual review of medicine*. 2024 Jan 29; 75(1): 307-19.
19. El-Shafie KT. Clinical presentation of hypothyroidism. *Journal of Family and Community Medicine*. 2003 Jan 1; 10(1): 55-8.
20. Counts D, Varma SK. Hypothyroidism in children. *Pediatrics in review*. 2009 Jul 1; 30(7): 251-8.
21. Hueston WJ. Treatment of hypothyroidism. *American family physician*. 2001 Nov 15; 64(10): 1717-25.
22. Vaidya B, Pearce SH. Management of hypothyroidism in adults. *Bmj*. 2008 Jul 28; 337.
23. Biondi B, Klein I. Hypothyroidism as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. *Endocrine*. 2004 Jun; 24(1): 1-3.
24. Davis LE, Leveno KJ, Cunningham FG. Hypothyroidism complicating pregnancy. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 1988 Jul; 72(1): 108-12.
25. Verma A, Jayaraman M, Modi KD. Hypothyroidism and obesity. Cause or effect?. *Saudi medical journal*. 2008; 29(8): 1135-8.